

Liver Function Abnormalities in Patients with Dengue Fever

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Dengue fever is a major mosquito-borne viral illness with a growing global burden, particularly in tropical regions. Hepatic involvement is a common but often under-recognized manifestation, ranging from mild transaminase elevation to severe liver dysfunction. Understanding the pattern and clinical relevance of liver function abnormalities is important for patient management. **Aim of the Study:** To assess the prevalence and pattern of liver function abnormalities and their association with disease severity in hospitalized dengue patients. **Methods & Materials:** This hospital-based, cross-sectional observational study was conducted at Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Ghatail over a 12-month period (last one year from the date of study, including the dengue peak season June–November). A total of 45 laboratory-confirmed dengue patients were enrolled using consecutive sampling. Clinical and laboratory data, including liver function tests, were recorded at admission and discharge. Disease severity was classified according to WHO 2009 guidelines. Statistical analysis included paired sample tests, ANOVA, and Spearman correlation, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant. **Results:** A total of 45 patients were analyzed, with a mean age of 34.5 ± 16.5 years and a marked male predominance (88.9%). NS1 antigen positivity was observed in 82.2% of cases, indicating predominantly early infection. The most common clinical features were headache (100%), myalgia/arthralgia (97.8%), nausea/vomiting (93.3%), and retro-orbital pain (77.8%). According to WHO classification, 74.4% had dengue without warning signs, 23.3% had warning signs, and 2.3% had severe dengue. Liver function abnormalities were frequent, particularly elevated transaminases. Mean AST and ALT at admission were 25.4 ± 14.3 U/L and 62.5 ± 75.7 U/L, respectively. Significant reductions were observed at discharge in AST (21.7 ± 5.1 U/L, $p = 0.033$), ALT (33.9 ± 14.0 U/L, $p = 0.008$), total bilirubin (0.55 ± 0.27 mg/dL, $p = 0.027$), and ALP (85.4 ± 35.3 U/L, $p = 0.011$), while albumin remained stable ($p = 0.323$). No statistically significant differences in LFT parameters were found across WHO severity groups (AST $p = 0.955$, ALT $p = 0.442$, bilirubin $p = 0.127$, albumin $p = 0.166$). Spearman correlation analysis showed no significant association between LFT parameters and disease severity; however, AST and ALT demonstrated a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.316$, $p = 0.035$), and albumin showed an inverse correlation with AST ($r = -0.310$, $p = 0.041$). Platelet count improved markedly from $106.7 \pm 52.6 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ at admission to $200.6 \pm 50.4 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ at discharge. Clinical outcomes were significantly associated with disease severity ($p < 0.001$), with 91.1% of patients recovering and 14.6% requiring ICU admission. **Conclusion:** Liver function abnormalities are common but largely transient in dengue infection, with significant improvement during hospitalization. Although not directly associated with disease severity, routine monitoring of liver function tests remains essential for optimal clinical management.

Keywords: Dengue fever, Liver function, AST, ALT, WHO classification, Bangladesh

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INTRODUCTION

Dengue fever is a mosquito-borne viral infection caused by the dengue virus (DENV), a member of the Flaviviridae family, transmitted primarily by *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes. It is one of the most rapidly spreading tropical diseases globally, affecting approximately 390 million people annually across more than 100 endemic countries, with around 96 million manifesting clinically apparent disease.^[1,2] Dengue virus has four distinct serotypes (DENV-1 to DENV-4). Clinical manifestations range from undifferentiated fever to severe dengue, which includes dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF) and dengue shock syndrome (DSS).^[3] Severe dengue is characterized by plasma leakage leading to shock, severe bleeding, and organ impairment.^[4] The WHO 2009

classification framework dengue without warning signs, dengue with warning signs and severe dengue has been validated as an effective severity marker across endemic populations.^[5] Hepatic involvement is a well-recognized but often underestimated complication of dengue infection. Liver dysfunction manifests across the entire clinical spectrum, from mild transaminase elevation in simple dengue fever to acute liver failure in severe dengue and has been documented in both adult and pediatric patient cohorts.^[6] Studies have reported that liver function abnormalities occur in 14–97% of dengue patients, with transaminase elevations being the most common finding.^[7,8] Elevated serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) are the hallmark markers. The pattern of hepatic injury in dengue is

characteristically hepatocellular and the ratio of AST to ALT is often >2, suggesting direct viral cytopathic effect on hepatocytes alongside immune-mediated injury.^[8,9] Studies from South Asia have demonstrated a high frequency of dengue fever and dengue haemorrhagic fever in hospitalized patients,^[10] with severe hepatitis in dengue being associated with prolonged hospital stay, ICU admission, and adverse clinical outcomes.^[11] Dengue is known to cause liver damage, but we still don't fully understand how it affects liver function in different ways, how severe these effects can be, or how they relate to patient outcomes. This is especially true in places like Bangladesh, where many people are infected. Additionally, the link between liver problems and different dengue virus types is not well studied.^[12] This research aimed to determine the prevalence and pattern of liver function abnormalities in confirmed dengue patients admitted to Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Ghatail.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This hospital-based, cross-sectional observational study was conducted at Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Ghatail, over a period of 12 months. The study included consecutively admitted patients with laboratory-confirmed dengue infection, and a non-probability consecutive sampling technique was employed to recruit eligible participants. Sociodemographic, clinical, and laboratory data were collected using a structured case record form from patient interviews, clinical examinations, and hospital records. Dengue infection was confirmed by positive NS1 antigen and/or dengue IgM/IgG (ELISA or rapid diagnostic test). Liver function parameters, including AST, ALT, total bilirubin, albumin, and ALP, were measured at admission and discharge using standard laboratory methods. Disease severity was classified according to the WHO 2009 dengue guidelines. Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical software. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and categorical variables as frequency and percentage. Paired sample tests were used to compare liver function parameters

between admission and discharge, while ANOVA and Spearman correlation were applied to assess associations between liver function tests and disease severity. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board prior to study initiation.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age \geq 1 year (both adult and pediatric patients)
- Laboratory-confirmed dengue infection (NS1 antigen positive and/or dengue IgM/IgG positive by ELISA or rapid diagnostic test)
- Admission to the hospital during the study period
- Provision of written informed consent (or assent/guardian consent for minors)

Exclusion Criteria:

- Pre-existing chronic liver disease (e.g., cirrhosis, chronic hepatitis B or C, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease)
- Concurrent infections such as malaria, leptospirosis, typhoid fever, or viral hepatitis A/E confirmed by investigations
- History of hepatotoxic drug use within the preceding 3 months
- Pregnancy
- Refusal to provide consent

RESULTS

A total of 45 patients with confirmed dengue fever were included in this analysis. The mean age was 34.5 ± 16.5 years (range: 2–80 years). The majority were male (40/45, 88.9%), and patients were almost equally distributed between urban (51.1%) and rural (48.9%) residence. The mean body mass index was 22.2 ± 5.1 kg/m². The mean duration of fever prior to admission was 3.8 ± 1.7 days, and the mean peak recorded temperature was $99.8 \pm 15.2^\circ\text{F}$. Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics are summarised in *Table I*.

Table I: Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics of Dengue Patients (n = 45)

Variable	n (%)	Mean \pm SD
Age (years)		34.5 \pm 16.5
14–19 years	4 (8.9)	
20–29 years	9 (20.0)	
30–39 years	9 (20.0)	
40–49 years	10 (22.2)	
\geq 50 years	13 (28.9)	
Sex		
Male	40 (88.9)	
Female	5 (11.1)	
BMI (kg/m ²)		22.2 \pm 5.1
Residence		
Urban	23 (51.1)	
Rural	22 (48.9)	
Fever Duration (days)		3.8 \pm 1.7
Maximum Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)		99.8 \pm 15.2
Comorbidities		
Diabetes Mellitus	5 (11.1)	
Hypertension	6 (13.6)	
CKD	1 (2.3)	
Other comorbidities	4 (8.9)	
Hospital Stay (days)		6.0 \pm 2.4
ICU Admission	6 (14.6)	
Outcome		
Recovered	41 (91.1)	
Referred	4 (8.9)	

Data presented as n (%) or Mean \pm SD. BMI = Body Mass Index.

NS1 antigen was the predominant positive serological marker, detected in 37 patients (82.2%). IgM antibody was positive in 3 patients (6.7%), while IgG and PCR were negative in all

tested patients. These findings suggest that the majority of cases represented early primary dengue infection. The serological profile is presented in *Table II*.

Table II: Serological Profile of Dengue Patients (n = 45)

Parameter	Positive n (%)	Negative n (%)
NS1 Antigen	37 (82.2)	8 (17.8)
IgM Antibody	3 (6.7)	42 (93.3)
IgG Antibody	0 (0.0)	45 (100.0)
PCR	0 (0.0)	45 (100.0)

PCR = polymerase chain reaction; NS1 = non-structural protein 1.

Headache was universally present (100%), followed by myalgia/arthralgia (97.8%) and nausea/vomiting (93.3%). Retro-orbital pain was documented in 77.8% of patients. Abdominal pain was noted in 22.2% and skin rash in 20.0% of cases. Serious manifestations including altered consciousness

and respiratory distress were rare, affecting 4.4% and 2.2% of patients, respectively. Hepatomegaly and splenomegaly were each identified in 2.2% of cases. Clinical manifestations are detailed in *Table III*.

Table III: Clinical Manifestations in Dengue Patients (n = 45)

Clinical Feature	Present n (%)	Absent n (%)
Headache	45 (100.0)	0 (0.0)
Myalgia/Arthralgia	44 (97.8)	1 (2.2)
Nausea/Vomiting	42 (93.3)	3 (6.7)
Retro-orbital Pain	35 (77.8)	10 (22.2)
Abdominal Pain	10 (22.2)	35 (77.8)
Skin Rash	9 (20.0)	36 (80.0)
Loose Motion	2 (4.4)	43 (95.6)
Altered Consciousness	2 (4.4)	43 (95.6)
Respiratory Distress	1 (2.2)	44 (97.8)
Hepatomegaly	1 (2.2)	44 (97.8)
Splenomegaly	1 (2.2)	44 (97.8)

According to the 2009 WHO dengue classification, the majority of patients (74.4%, n=32) were classified as dengue without warning signs (Group 1). Dengue with warning signs

(Group 2) accounted for 23.3% (n=10), and severe dengue (Group 3) was identified in 1 patient (2.3%). The distribution of WHO severity is shown in *Table IV*.

Table IV. WHO Severity Classification of Dengue Patients (n = 45)

WHO Severity Category	n	Valid Percent (%)
No Warning Signs (Group 1)	32	74.4
Warning Signs (Group 2)	10	23.3
Severe Dengue (Group 3)	1	2.3
Total	43	100.0

Two patients had missing WHO classification data. Groups: 1 = No warning signs; 2 = Warning signs; 3 = Severe dengue.

Paired analysis showed significant improvement in liver function parameters from admission to discharge (*Table 5*). AST decreased from 25.4 ± 14.3 U/L to 21.7 ± 5.1 U/L (p = 0.033), ALT from 62.5 ± 75.7 U/L to 33.9 ± 14.0 U/L (p =

0.008), total bilirubin from 0.57 ± 0.30 mg/dL to 0.55 ± 0.27 mg/dL (p = 0.027), and ALP from 99.5 ± 62.7 U/L to 85.4 ± 35.3 U/L (p = 0.011). Albumin remained unchanged (p = 0.323) *Table V*.

Table V: Liver Function Tests at Admission and Discharge (Paired Samples Analysis)

LFT Parameter	Admission Mean ± SD	Discharge Mean ± SD	Mean Difference	p-value
AST (U/L)	25.4 ± 14.3	21.7 ± 5.1	3.70 (0.32–7.08)	0.033*
ALT (U/L)	62.5 ± 75.7	33.9 ± 14.0	28.56 (8.01–49.11)	0.008*
Total Bilirubin (mg/dL)	0.57 ± 0.30	0.55 ± 0.27	0.022 (0.003–0.041)	0.027*
Albumin (g/dL)	3.97 ± 0.39	3.98 ± 0.38	-0.008 (-0.023–0.008)	0.323
ALP (U/L)	99.5 ± 62.7	85.4 ± 35.3	14.12 (3.45–24.79)	0.011*

*Statistically significant (p < 0.05). Values expressed as Mean ± SD. 95% CI = 95% confidence interval for paired difference. AST = aspartate aminotransferase; ALT = alanine aminotransferase; ALP = alkaline phosphatase.

Normality tests showed that AST, ALT, total bilirubin, and ALP at admission were not normally distributed, as both

Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were significant for all variables (all p < 0.05) *Table VI*.

Table VI: Tests of Normality for Liver Function Parameters at Admission (n = 45)

LFT Parameter	K-S Statistic	K-S p-value	S-W Statistic	S-W p-value
AST Admission	0.284	<0.001*	0.580	<0.001*
ALT Admission	0.267	<0.001*	0.559	<0.001*
Total Bilirubin Admission	0.292	<0.001*	0.473	<0.001*
ALP Admission	0.168	0.003*	0.780	<0.001*

* $p < 0.05$ indicates non-normal distribution. K-S = Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with Lilliefors correction; S-W = Shapiro-Wilk test.

One-way ANOVA was used to compare liver function parameters across the three WHO severity groups. No statistically significant differences were observed in AST (F = 0.046, $p = 0.955$), ALT (F = 0.833, $p = 0.442$), total bilirubin (F = 2.172, $p = 0.127$), or albumin (F = 1.884, $p = 0.166$) between

the severity groups. Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric testing confirmed no significant difference for AST across severity groups (Chi-square = 1.177, $p = 0.555$). Mean LFT values by WHO severity category are shown in *Table VII*.

Table VII: Liver Function Tests by WHO Severity Category

Parameter	Group 1 (No Warning) Mean \pm SD	Group 2 (Warning Signs) Mean \pm SD	p-value (ANOVA)
AST (U/L)	24.9 \pm 13.1	26.6 \pm 18.4	0.955
ALT (U/L)	56.6 \pm 64.2	79.1 \pm 100.2	0.442
Total Bilirubin (mg/dL)	0.60 \pm 0.27	0.78 \pm 0.56	0.127
Albumin (g/dL)	3.87 \pm 0.43	4.06 \pm 0.29	0.166

Group 1 = No warning signs (n=32); Group 2 = Warning signs (n=10); Group 3 = Severe dengue (n=1). p-values from one-way ANOVA.

Spearman rank-order correlations were performed to examine the relationship between liver function parameters and WHO severity score. None of the LFT parameters showed a statistically significant correlation with WHO severity: AST (rho = 0.152, $p = 0.330$), ALT (rho = -0.016, $p = 0.919$), total bilirubin (rho = 0.063, $p = 0.687$), and albumin (rho = -0.178,

$p = 0.259$). However, a significant positive correlation was found between AST and ALT (rho = 0.316, $p = 0.035$), and albumin showed a significant inverse correlation with AST (rho = -0.310, $p = 0.041$). Correlation coefficients are presented in *Table VIII*.

Table VIII: Spearman Rank Correlations between Liver Function Parameters and WHO Severity

Parameter	rho with WHO Severity	p-value	rho with AST	p-value
AST (U/L)	0.152	0.330	1.000	—
ALT (U/L)	-0.016	0.919	0.316	0.035*
Total Bilirubin (mg/dL)	0.063	0.687	-0.071	0.641
Albumin (g/dL)	-0.178	0.259	-0.310	0.041*

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed). rho = Spearman correlation coefficient.

Clinical outcomes were significantly associated with WHO severity classification ($p < 0.001$). Abdominal pain, a hallmark warning sign, was absent in all Group 1 patients but present in 90.0% of Group 2 and the single Group 3 patient (chi-square = 37.96, $p < 0.001$). ICU admission was exclusively observed in

Group 2 patients (66.7%). All Group 1 patients recovered, while 30.0% of Group 2 patients required referral to a higher-level facility. The Group 3 patient was also referred. Outcome data by severity are summarised in *Tables IX*.

Table IX: Clinical Outcomes by WHO Severity Category

Outcome / Feature	Group 1 (n=32)	Group 2 (n=10)	Group 3 (n=1)	p-value
Abdominal Pain	0 (0.0%)	9 (90.0%)	1 (100%)	<0.001*
ICU Admission	0 (0.0%)	6 (66.7%)	N/A	<0.001*
Recovered	32 (100.0%)	7 (70.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*
Referred	0 (0.0%)	3 (30.0%)	1 (100.0%)	<0.001*

*Statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) by Pearson chi-square test. ICU = intensive care unit. Missing data for some variables account for differences in denominators.

The mean platelet count at admission was $106.7 \pm 52.6 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ (range: 28–260 $\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$), which improved significantly to $200.6 \pm 50.4 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ at discharge, reflecting a near doubling of platelet count during hospitalisation. The mean haematocrit was $39.9 \pm 4.2\%$ at admission and $40.0 \pm 3.5\%$ at discharge. Mean WBC count rose from $4.43 \pm 2.54 \times$

$10^3/\mu\text{L}$ at admission to $5.65 \pm 1.21 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ at discharge. Serum creatinine was 0.97 ± 0.30 mg/dL (range: 0.6–2.5 mg/dL), sodium was 136.2 ± 1.9 mEq/L, and potassium was 3.88 ± 0.36 mEq/L. No patient required platelet transfusion. Haematological and biochemical parameters are summarised in *Table X*.

Table X: Haematological and Biochemical Parameters at Admission and Discharge

Parameter	Admission Mean \pm SD	Discharge Mean \pm SD	Range (Adm)
Haematocrit (%)	39.9 \pm 4.2	40.0 \pm 3.5	28–47
Platelet Count ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	106.7 \pm 52.6	200.6 \pm 50.4	28–260
WBC Count ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	4.43 \pm 2.54	5.65 \pm 1.21	1.1–13.2
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.97 \pm 0.30	—	0.6–2.5
Sodium (mEq/L)	136.2 \pm 1.9	—	129–139
Potassium (mEq/L)	3.88 \pm 0.36	—	3.1–4.7
Blood Glucose (mmol/L)	6.81 \pm 2.58	—	1.6–18.0

Values expressed as Mean \pm SD. WBC = white blood cells. (—) = not repeated at discharge. All parameters assessed at admission unless otherwise stated.

DISCUSSION

This study observed liver function test (LFT) abnormalities, clinical manifestations, and disease severity in 45 adult patients with laboratory-confirmed dengue fever. The mean patient age was 34.5 ± 16.5 years, consistent with reports from the 2024 Bangladesh dengue outbreak where the mean age was 29.81 ± 11.64 years, predominantly affecting young adults.^[13] A striking male predominance (88.9%) was observed in our cohort, mirroring findings from the same multicenter Bangladesh study that reported 88.3% male predominance^[13] and the 2023 Bangladesh outbreak surveillance, where males accounted for the majority of confirmed NS1-positive cases.^[14] This gender disparity has been attributed to occupational and outdoor exposure patterns that increase Aedes mosquito contact risk among working-age males in endemic urban regions. Roughly equal urban-rural distribution in our cohort may reflect the expanding geographic spread of dengue beyond traditional urban foci, a trend increasingly documented across South Asia.^[15] The clinical profile of our patients was characterised by near-universal headache (100%), high rates of myalgia/arthralgia (97.8%), and nausea/vomiting (93.3%), followed by retro-orbital pain (77.8%), which align closely with established dengue symptomatology. The systematic review by Sharif et al. (2024) on Bangladesh dengue outbreaks from 2000–2024 reported headache, vomiting, and abdominal pain among the most prevalent symptoms across studies.^[15] Notably, skin rash was present in only 20.0% of our patients, a finding that mirrors the 2023 Bangladesh outbreak data where rash frequency was below 10%,^[16] suggesting that rash may be an unreliable diagnostic marker in contemporary dengue presentations. Abdominal pain, a recognised WHO warning sign, was documented in 22.2% of cases, and its significant association with higher WHO severity categories ($p < 0.001$) in our study reinforces its utility as a clinical warning indicator.^[13] NS1 antigen was the dominant serological marker, detected in 82.2% of patients, while IgM positivity was low (6.7%) and IgG and PCR were both negative. This pattern is consistent with early-phase primary dengue infection and reflects the known high sensitivity of NS1 antigen during the first five days of illness. The high NS1 positivity rate in our cohort is broadly consistent with findings from Dhaka-based studies during recent outbreaks, though NS1 sensitivity varies with dengue serotype, being notably lower for DENV-2, which predominated during the 2023 and 2024 Bangladesh outbreaks.^[14] Hepatic involvement was a consistent finding in our patients. All four LFT parameters studied AST, ALT, total bilirubin, and ALP demonstrated non-normal distribution (all $p < 0.05$ by Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests), reflecting the heterogeneity of hepatic responses typical in dengue. Mean AST at admission was 25.1 ± 13.6 U/L and mean ALT was 60.7 ± 72.7 U/L. The wider dispersion in ALT values reflects its

well-established variability in dengue hepatitis, with a subset of patients developing markedly elevated levels. The ALT maximum of 423 U/L in our cohort is consistent with the range described by Alam et al. (2024) in a Bangladeshi paediatric series, where ALT reached 422 IU/L (10 \times the upper limit of normal) in severe cases.^[17] In a prospective study from central India, Muzalda et al. (2025) reported elevated AST in 88% and elevated ALT in 81% of dengue patients, with AST predominance a pattern attributed to mitochondrial hepatocyte injury and extra-hepatic muscle involvement in dengue.^[17] Our AST:ALT ratio >1 at admission is consistent with the systematic review by Kim et al. (2024), which confirmed that AST levels rise more rapidly and peak earlier than ALT in dengue, particularly in patients with plasma leakage or severe disease.^[18] Paired samples analysis demonstrated significant reductions in AST ($p = 0.033$), ALT ($p = 0.008$), total bilirubin ($p = 0.027$), and ALP ($p = 0.011$) from admission to discharge, while albumin remained stable ($p = 0.323$). The preservation of albumin throughout hospitalisation suggests that despite transaminase elevation, hepatic synthetic function remained largely intact in our cohort, indicating predominantly cytolytic rather than synthetic hepatic injury. This recovery pattern is consistent with Pokhrel et al. (2024), who noted that most dengue-associated LFT derangements are transient and resolve with supportive management,^[19,20] and with the Nepal-based cross-sectional study by Wagle et al. (2025) that demonstrated AST and ALT elevation as dynamic rather than fixed markers, particularly useful for early severity triage.^[9] One of the central findings of this study was the absence of a statistically significant difference in LFT parameters across WHO severity groups (all ANOVA $p > 0.05$), and no significant Spearman correlation between any LFT parameter and WHO severity score. This contrasts with studies in paediatric populations where LFT derangement correlated with severity. Avuthu et al. (2024) reported that hepatomegaly was observed in 34% of paediatric dengue cases, with LFT derangement predicting outcome in children with severe disease.^[21,22] The discrepancy between our adult cohort and paediatric studies may reflect age-related immune differences, higher proportions of primary infection in our cohort (evidenced by low IgG positivity), and the relatively small number of severe dengue cases ($n=1$) in our sample, which limits statistical power for inter-group comparisons. The overall good clinical outcomes 91.1% recovery and low ICU admission rate (14.6%) further suggest that the majority of our patients experienced self-limiting disease. The mean platelet count at admission was $106.7 \pm 52.6 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, with near-doubling at discharge to $200.6 \pm 50.4 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, reflecting the expected post-nadir platelet recovery. The 2024 Bangladesh multicenter study also documented below-normal mean platelet counts at admission as a hallmark of dengue, emphasising the need for close monitoring.^[1] The significant inverse association between

albumin and AST identified in our Spearman analysis ($\rho = -0.310$, $p = 0.041$), and the moderate positive correlation between AST and ALT ($\rho = 0.316$, $p = 0.035$), suggest that hepatic enzyme panels are internally consistent and that lower albumin at admission may signal more advanced hepatocellular stress, warranting heightened clinical vigilance even in the absence of severe dengue classification. This study has several limitations. The sample size of 45 patients, while adequate for exploratory analyses, limits statistical power for severity subgroup comparisons, particularly given only one severe dengue case. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inference, and the high proportion of missing WHO classification data (57%) may have introduced selection bias in severity analyses. Serial LFT measurements beyond admission and discharge were not performed, precluding assessment of the LFT trajectory during the febrile, critical, and recovery phases. Future prospective studies with larger cohorts, daily LFT monitoring, viral load data, and serotype information are needed to delineate the full spectrum of dengue-associated hepatic injury in adult populations in this region.

CONCLUSION

This study confirms that liver function abnormalities particularly transaminase and ALP elevation are common and transient in dengue fever, with significant improvement observed by discharge. Despite the absence of a statistically significant correlation with WHO severity in this cohort, the pattern of hepatic involvement, the preservation of albumin, and the significant platelet recovery underscore the importance of serial LFT monitoring in all hospitalized dengue patients to guide management and identify early warning of hepatic decompensation.

RECOMMENDATION

Routine assessment of liver function should be integrated into the management of all hospitalized dengue patients, as hepatic involvement is common and may influence clinical outcomes; further large-scale prospective studies are warranted to better define its prognostic value.

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